

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON E-COMMERCE MARKETING

Osman Doruk

Dokuz Eylul University Instructor

Certified Public Accountant - Independent Auditor

St Clements University Associate Professor of Business

Turhan Zahid ÖZKİRAZ

St Clements University PhD Student

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Abstract

Social media tools: It is an e-commerce platform that increases people's interest in the demand for products with its features such as facilitating organization, enabling the rapid spread of ideas, contributing to the increase of communication between individuals, reducing the costs of organization and propaganda, enabling more people to react to innovative ideas and products in a shorter time. -The features of social media marketing, which is important in commerce, customer relations in social media platforms and the concept of social media and its effect on the purchasing process are discussed in a comprehensive way. While using the marketing methods that will increase the sales in the social media, the main factors that the ecommerce site should pay attention to both for marketing and advertising activities have been examined together with social media commerce. With the relationship of e-commerce and social media marketing, social networks where consumers are increasingly shopping online, connecting with various brands, and directing users to them. This gives us an important clue about the relationship between e-commerce and social media commerce.

Keywords: *E-commerce, Digital marketing, e-marketing, social media marketing, social media marketing tools, social media impact, social media concept*

1. Introduction

Social networks are used by businesses to transmit and disseminate their marketing messages. as a unique supporting element in realizing their presentations and managing their brand image. finds place. Social networks are for 'networking'. Social networks allow people to communicate with each other.

It is the old-fashioned networking style that allows people to get to know each other better. For businesses, this

to establish new relationships with potential customers and to improve the products of existing satisfied customers.

means increasing sales. The importance of communication between businesses and customers to create the concept of trust with the customer, to gain the understanding of the customers, to be preferred

It is about increasing rates, providing reminders, raising awareness and persuading. Businesses

Therefore, they give increasing importance to social media channels in developing relationships (Akar, 2010:147). With the rapid development of technology, social media played a key role in its development. Businesses can market their products/services, brands, and target have started to develop new strategies through social media to reach the masses (Berthon et al., 2012:265).

2. Conceptual Framework of social media

2.1. Social Media Concept

As it is known, our world is now called the age of technology, information, and communication. Studies on this subject have now become a major source of studies of science branches. Social media: The age of communication, innovations in this field and their effects are contained in these three phenomena. Social media is declared as a structure or online communication channel resembling an interactive structure, with the participation of target audiences, hosting groups and connecting these groups to each other. (Kalafatoğlu, 2010: 17). According to Blackshaw and Nazarro (2004). and social media; It is “the place and emerging online information resources that consumers create, initiate, disseminate, and use, who intend to educate each other about products, brands, services, people, and topics” (Blackshaw and Nazarro, 2004: 2).

Social media can be broadly expressed as a source of social interaction, which allows for a deep social connection, community formation, and collaboration projects built on Web 2.0 technologies. (Akar, 2010: 17).

Social media can also be named as mobile-based and internet tools and tools that connect social interaction, technology, and telecommunications by enabling the production of sounds, the dissemination and co-production of words and images (still and moving) (Dabner, 2012: 69).

Social media is a platform where, with the technical invention developed by the internet in recent years, internet users can access, use, share and communicate easily with sites such as YouTube and Facebook. The domain is web 2.0 based.(Aysel Aziz, 2010, p.134)

The new version of the web, which is approved as a "new technology" according to other names, and "a new age" according to other names; It is characterized as providing users with the opportunity to produce content according to their own demands, share their own perspectives, produce their own ideas, and add different perspectives (Jalali, 2009:198).

Users were able to actively participate in the enrichment and creation of websites (Adebanjo & Michaelides, 2010).

Thus, Web 2.0 sites are called as sites that allow users to interfere with their content holistically (Oftade, 2009: 138).

While there is a structure starting from the bottom up with Web 2.0 tools, and the user in this structure does not meet technical interventions, and their content can be published, as well as an environment where they can benefit from service and social interaction applications that provide cooperation, while the I. Generation web tools have a top-down structure. , participants are passive . (Murphy, 2000: 89).

2.2. Features of social media

In general, social media is an information system that offers the latest ideas, new opportunities and possibilities and realizes the highest level of sharing. (Akıncı Vural and Bat, 2010: 3352) and includes the following features:

Participation: By shaking the lines between social media and its audience, it makes it easier for the users to contribute to the feedbacks of the individuals with whom they are contacted (Hazar, 2011: 157).

Openness: many social media are open to feedback and participation. aims to interpret, share, and vote information.(Akar, 2010: 18).

Conversation: Traditional media often involves multi-purpose communication. In social media, people provide comfortable and timely feedback, two-way communication, and feedback in mass media takes time and is exceedingly difficult (Hazar, 2011: 157).

Society: social media enables communities as an effective and fast formation, and this community shares the values that individuals are related to, such as favorite TV, political values, photography, with their loved ones (Akıncı Vural and Bat, 2010: 3352).

Connectivity: social media is integrated in many places. Due to many reasons, it creates connectivity for individuals by using values such as resources, links, communication to other sites, user friendliness and advertising (Hazar, 2011: 157).

2.3. Importance of social media

Social media is an environment where users exchange information and ideas with each other and talk on a wide variety of topics, from commerce to health, from education to entertainment. Social media gets its power from its users. Therefore, social media is important for both businesses and consumers. In social media platforms, businesses can easily and easily share their experiences, thoughts, satisfaction, or dissatisfaction about the goods and / or services they buy, while communicating with consumers by doing some marketing activities to ensure the purchase of goods and / or services, that is, the preference of the business.

In short, social media is an important medium that has an impact on consumers' pre- and post-purchase behavior in favor or against businesses. For this reason, businesses can make it an important advantage for consumers by taking an active role in social media and using social media effectively. For online communication enthusiasts, businesses can promote their products and services and provide support via social media through social networking sites, social

marking sites, news sites, forums, and gaming sites. In addition, social media can be used to share information with consumers about product and service brands, thanks to their followers. Communication between followers can be considered as an effective way to provide cost-effectiveness to companies, increase brand awareness and build brand loyalty. For these reasons, it can be said that social media helps companies to create brand loyalty. (<http://www.yazete.com/genc-kalemler/yusuf-temrel/socialmedyanin-gunumuzdeki-onemi/671>).

2.4. Historical Development of social media

With the emergence of the internet and the development of the web, the concept of social media has also emerged, and it has made progress day by day with technological developments and new software.

The internet, which moved from Web 1 to Web 2, allowed its users to interact with each other. The historical development of social media, which was first accepted as the beginning of the emergence of sixdegrees.com in 1997, is clearly presented in the figure below.

The historical development of social media affects all aspects of marketing such as advertising, public relations, brand communication and consumer behavior. For this reason, the social media platform has immense importance in marketing.

Şekil 22: Sosyal Medyanın Tarihsel Gelişimi

Figure 1.1: Historical Development of social media¹

2.5. Difference between social media and Traditional Media

Radio, TV, newspapers, and magazines, which are described as traditional media, are watched, read, and listened to by passive readers. The direction of the message has changed bidirectionally, only from the source to the destination. This event started to become increasingly disturbing over time, ignoring the problems, demands, expectations, opinions and ideas of the audience, readers and listeners, and trust in traditional media forms gradually decreased (Akar, 2010: 35).

Social media instead of an informatics that makes the traditional media one-way message and target audience passive; It has removed the shortcomings of traditional media by allowing millions of individuals gathered from the circle of hobbies, interests, passions, political views, and businesses to establish two-way communication at once (2010:10).

Social media and traditional media are constantly confused because of the differences between them. this approach is especially important in the sense that it usually distinguishes, creates, and comprehends the two factors being compared in a clear line.

2.6. Social Media Measurement Studies and Its Importance

The change and development of the developing information environment has increased the interest in information and communication technology from all people and in this context, the power in social media has increased, and the concept of socialization, which is a new dimension, has gained.

In a way, the individual has become a high-level goal for marketing and advertising activities and has developed a communication network by socializing. After understanding the power of social media and digital media in this context, the world of commerce defines people in more three-dimensional ways and gains an ever-deepening learning network; by having more knowledge and skills; He wanted to continue his consumption base and reign by having his demands and dominance approved by him.

Many businesses are aware that today, by not following the perception of social media, their survival will be realized by the metaphor of a ship that will be lacking in radar capabilities and the lack of opportunities to destroy threats and research, such as heading towards a destination without navigation.

With the increasing popularity and emergence of new communication opportunities, the tools in social media have started to use the communication model widely between individuals and corporate organizations. The popularity of social media in measuring effectiveness comes in

¹ Source: www.danah.org/papers/JCMIntro.pdf, Accessed: 09.12.2013

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the form of the biggest challenge facing researchers and business professionals in the field. A few researchers have categorized media measures as outcome, output, and exclusions.

Social media analytics; user data blogs microblogs (Twitter, Wetpaint), social news (Digg, Mixx), (Blogger, LiveJournal), opinion/opinion sites (ePinions, Yelp), social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn), social bookmarking (Delicious, CiteULike), wiki applications (Wikipedia, Wetpaint) and multimedia sharing (Flickr, Youtube). Social media uses this type of analytics to generate actionable and data analytics. Social media analytics are especially important to users and an excellent value to keep on social media.

2.7. Advantages of social media

While social media environments, which have a large user base, offer advantages to both individual users and businesses, there are also disadvantages if not used carefully.

It is possible to list the advantages of social media as follows (Bostancı, 2010: 44– 46).

- Social media is fast.
- Social media is up to date.
- Social media is cheap.
- Social media is dependable.
- Social media facilitates communication.
- Social media improves company image.
- Social media allows businesses to follow the opinions of their brands in real time.

Social media enables businesses to deliver effective messages to their target audiences.

- Social media saves businesses from being tied to a single market.
- Social media gives users the opportunity to create audiences, both individually and on a business basis.
- Social media provides the opportunity to interact with the world.
- For businesses, social media offers the opportunity to respond to customer requests and needs more easily.

2.8. Disadvantages of social media

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The disadvantages of social media can be listed as follows:

1. *Social media is difficult to follow and control because it spreads very quickly,*
2. *Lack of privacy of private life,*
3. *Violation of copyright / patent rights,*
4. *Not showing the original source of the content,*
5. *The dissemination of the produced content before it is mature and its accuracy is confirmed,*
6. *The blurring of the boundaries of news and commercial information,*
7. *Exposing the user to intense advertising with new media features,*
8. *Reproduction of gender inequality,*
9. *Misleading labeling of content,*
10. *Increasing hate speech against certain groups,*
11. *The spread of careless use of language,*
12. *Positioning the individual as a consumer in the new media environment,*
13. *For businesses, the negative impact of an incorrectly chosen message is greater than normal*

It is necessary to focus on social media to reach the final goal,

Loss of workforce due to employees spending time on social networks during working hours,

Disclosure of companies' trade secrets in these environments,

Creation of the fake blog of the company to harm the companies,

2.9. Social Media Environments

There are several types of social media commonly used on the Internet. These:

Types of social media	Applications
Social Networking Sites	Facebook, Google+ (Plus) Myspace, Linkeden, Bebo, Orkut

Photo and Video Sharing	Youtube, Flickr, Instagram, Yahoo, SlideShare,
blogs	blogger, Wordpress, Timblr, TypePad
microblogging	Twitter, Plurk, Yammer
Virtual Life and Game Worlds	Second Life, ActiveWorlds, Miniclip
Wikis	Wikipedia
podcast	itunes
Social News	Digg,Reddit,

2.9.1. Social Networking Sites

It is called a website that introduces individuals on the internet, makes contact, brings together, creates groups, discusses, comments, provides information, enables people to exchange and exchange the produced content, and provides opportunities to appear in different environments for a product produced.

Social networking sites and sites give people the opportunity to share links within a limited system, to examine and view these shares in the users list within the system, and to create a public or semi-public profile.

2.10. Summary of Time Spent on social media

People spend an average of 2 hours and 32 minutes a day on social media. (“Why is social media so easily accessible? Part 1”)

4.2 billion people use social media (about 55% of the world's population).

Due to the global epidemic and social isolation, 81% of people spend more time on social media every day.

The average person spends the most time per day on YouTube (44 minutes), followed by Facebook (35 minutes), Instagram (33 minutes), TikTok (32 minutes) and Twitter (10 minutes).

Young people spend most of their time on social media; an average of 3 hours and 1 minute per day.

Some teens spend up to 9 hours a day on social media.

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The Philippines is the country that spends the most time on social media; an average of 3 hours and 53 minutes per day.

The average American spends 2 hours and 4 minutes a day on social media.

More than 270 million social media users suffer from social media addiction.

2.9.2 What is the Average Time Spent on social media in 2021?

The average time spent on social media continues to increase. The latest statistics show that people globally now spend an average of 2 hours 32 minutes a day on social media in 2021.

This is an increase of 7 minutes (5%) in daily time spent on social media from 2020, and an increase of more than an hour (69%) per day since 2012.

In the last few years, the growth in the time people spend on social media has started to stagnate. But in a recent survey, 81% of people admit that they spend more time on social media due to the global pandemic and social isolation. It shows that the Coronavirus (COVID-19) is contributing to the increase in the amount of time the average person spends on social media in

2021. (<https://famemass.com/time-spent-on-social-media/>) Which Countries

Spend the Most Time on social media?

1. *Philippines – 3 hours*

53 minutes a day Brazil

– 3 hours 46 minutes a

day

2. *Nigeria – 3 hours 36 minutes a day*

3. *Colombia – 3 hours 36 minutes a day*

4. *Argentina – 3 hours 27 minutes a day*

5. *Why Does the Average Person Use social media?*

A recent survey revealed the top seven reasons to use social media. Here are the details, the rate of those who say the following among the reasons for using social media is as follows:

1. *Forty percent – To be informed about current news and events*
2. *Thirty-nine percent – Staying in touch with what your friends are doing*
3. *Thirty-eight percent – To find funny or entertaining content*
4. *Thirty-seven percent – To fill free time*
5. *Thirty-three percent – Other people's public networks*
6. *Thirty-one percent – For sharing photos and videos with others*
7. *Twenty-nine percent – To find/research products to buy*

In the Nielsen statistics report, due to the increase in the use of social media over time, the concept of social media marketing has emerged with this interaction in e-commerce sites.

3. Social Media Marketing

Social Media is an area where the importance of brands increases day by day and serious investments are made in this sector. Today, it is among the platforms where the most effective marketing activities take place. (“What Is the Digital Marketing? - euromsg express”) Social Media Marketing is the process of promoting a product or service on social media networks, advertising, increasing brand awareness, etc. It is a marketing method in which transactions are conducted. In other words, all marketing strategies made through social media platforms are called 'Social Media Marketing'.²

1. *Advantages of Social Media Marketing*
2. *Social media marketing provides many advantages for both corporate companies and e-commerce companies.*

² (<https://pazarlamaturkiye.com/social-medya-pazarlamasi-nedir-ornekler-ve-stratejileri-nedir/>)

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3. *The main advantages of social media marketing to brands are:*
4. *Thanks to social media marketing, businesses reach the people in their target audiences more easily.*
 5. *Brands constantly communicate with their target audiences and followers by marketing activities on social media.*
 6. *It is extremely easy for brands to create their own audiences and to create this audience.*
 7. *E-commerce companies or corporate companies increase their brand reputation through social media activities.*
 8. *E-commerce companies that determine their digital marketing strategies well can compete with their competitors more easily.*
 9. *E-commerce companies or corporate brands can attract traffic to their sites by doing social media marketing.*
 10. *Social media marketing helps brands increase their sales.*
 11. *Because it provides such advantages, every brand should take advantage of social media marketing to promote their product, service, or brand.*

How is Social Media Marketing Done?

Brands looking for social media marketing tips for e-commerce sites should first develop their marketing strategies professionally. While developing the marketing strategy, businesses should:

- i. Audience Analysis***
- ii. Competitor analysis***
- iii. Communication Platforms***
- iv. Sharing Quality***

It should act by analyzing basic processes such as Let us take a closer look at these crucial factors in social media marketing for e-commerce sites.

- v. Analyze Your Audience***

E-commerce sites usually work on people who want to sell their products and services or want to create brand awareness while doing social media studies. For this reason, every brand needs to analyze its target audience well.

- vi. Demographic information***
- vii. Internet usage habits***

Considering elements such as social media platforms, brands limit their target audiences and thus can make more successful social media marketing efforts.

- viii. Competitor analysis***

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Businesses operating in every sector have certain competitors. To know these competitors well and to develop a successful social media strategy, e-commerce companies should give importance to competitor analysis. When analyzing competitors, brands should analyze their strengths and weaknesses along with their social media marketing strategies.

ix. Deciding on Platforms to Conduct Communication

Every brand that wants to benefit from Social Media Marketing Tips for E-commerce Sites should act according to the platforms on which it will share and conduct digital marketing activities. When deciding on these platforms, it is important for businesses that will do social media marketing for e-commerce sites to consider their target audience and competitors.

x. Methods to Increase Sales on social media for E-commerce Sites

For e-commerce sites, there are marketing methods that will increase sales in social media. Every process from images to sharing descriptions, from hashtags to the features used helps to increase sales. Sharing images

xi. Sharing descriptions

xii. Hashtags

xiii. Features

xiv. Advertising works

xv. Every element like helps to increase sales on social media for e-commerce sites.

xvi. Pay Attention to Sharing Images on social media

For e-commerce sites, visuals are at the forefront of the marketing tactics that will increase sales in social media. E-commerce companies must give confidence to the people in their target audience to make more sales. For this reason, brands should constantly share and use reassuring visuals in these shares.

For this reason, brands should take care to shoot professional products and use these images in their sharing.

xvii. Care About Post Descriptions

As in your e-commerce site, you need to give importance to explanations to increase sales on social media. While some of the people who want to shop on your e-commerce site read the descriptions of the products they want to buy, most of the people who want to shop on social media decide on the post descriptions. A faster experience is provided about the product with social interaction.

Since post descriptions are effective in direct sales, e-commerce companies should take care to use post descriptions with call-to-action texts in which they promote their products.

xviii. Use Hashtags

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#Hashtags created by putting a '#' sign in front of a word affect sales positively. Because using #hashtag makes it easier to reach your products and services. For this reason, you should take care to use #hashtags in your posts while sharing.

xix. Advertise

Among the Social Media Marketing Tips for E-commerce Sites, the advertisements we will share with you both enable you to reach your target audience and help increase sales. For this reason, it is especially important for every e-commerce company to advertise for their shares.

Advantages of Social Media Marketing for Businesses

The most critical issue in marketing promotion activities is to communicate with existing and potential customers without time and place restrictions and to increase brand awareness. In line with these purposes, one of the tools that businesses can use to reach their goals is social media platforms (Barutçu and Tomaş, 2013:12). In addition to traditional media tools such as television, radio, magazines and newspapers, businesses today have enabled social media platforms to establish effective marketing communication with social media tools that offer the opportunity to interact with consumers (Dholakia and Bagozzi, 2001:167). Apart from traditional media tools, social media tools have brought a new perspective to the marketing approaches of companies. The innovations and features offered by the Internet differ from traditional media tools. It has also provided opportunities for communication and relationship building with social content, such as direct communication between individuals and institutions. Social media tools also offer opportunities to businesses for sales promotion activities. Businesses can choose a target audience for their sales promotion activities and special campaigns can reach the target audience thanks to social media (Köksal and Özdemir, 2013:325). Social networks create significant opportunities and opportunities for businesses for their commercial and economic activities. Businesses can increase the popularity of their websites and services by sharing information and prices about their products and services (Lea et al., 2006: 125). Social media tools provide opportunities for businesses to strengthen their relations with consumers and to increase the degree of sincerity. Thanks to this, businesses can influence their current and potential customers and increase their brand loyalty (Davis et al., 2010:42). Companies using social media platforms can direct people to positive thoughts about their brands by communicating interactively. As these people recommend the brand to other users on social media and share their experiences, it also affects the purchasing behavior of other social media users (Aytan and Telci, 2014:2). The fact that social media platforms are a part of consumers' lives today creates important opportunities for companies. It is not a necessity for companies to use social media, but it is also valuable in terms of strengthening their brand images and providing prestige (Dholakia and Bagozzi, 2001: 167). It is known that virtual communities are an effective resource for strategic decision making, as businesses can generate income by advertising in the online community. Thanks to this, customer relations are developed, consumer behaviors can be interpreted and customers' participation in new product development processes can be realized (Akar, 2010).

xx. *Social Media Marketing Methods for E-commerce Sites*

Although the Marketing Methods to Increase Sales in social media for E-commerce Sites are quite wide, it is known that Influencer Marketing and Affiliate Marketing are mostly used in addition to social media advertising today.

Influencer Marketing: It is a digital marketing method where brands promote their products, services, and brands by collaborating with social media accounts with high followers. It helps them expand their target audience.

Affiliate Marketing: It is a marketing method built by e-commerce companies with an affiliate program. People sign up for the program and get profit from every user's shopping that comes through their link.

You can set up Influencer and Affiliate Marketing, which are among the most used marketing methods in ecommerce, to increase sales on social media. Thus, you can reach your target audience and get the opportunity to make more sales. (www.ticimax.com/blog/e-commerce-sites-for-social-media-marketing-tips),

1. Conclusion

To understand the social media impact, we have comprehensively examined the concept of social media, its features, advantages, and disadvantages. The historical development of these platforms and how e-marketing progressed were discussed in detail. Social media marketing has created a new field for the ecommerce marketing method, which e-commerce companies or corporate brands conduct on social media platforms to create brand awareness, reach people in their target audience, make sales, and compete with their competitors. The marketing policies to be applied to the citizens are presented to a public vote through social media, and product diversification and the emergence of new products can be guided by the reaction of the citizens. E-commerce sites often use social media platforms to reach people in their target audience. The increasing use of social media platforms increases the importance of social media in the sales and marketing efforts of brands. Nowadays, many e-commerce companies are communicating and advertising on social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn to market products and services and create brand awareness.

While using the marketing methods that will increase the sales of the e-commerce site in the social media, there are the main factors that should be considered for both communication and advertising activities. Social commerce. "In other words, we can say that it is not only a purchase, but also a marketing activity through referral." ("2022 Engagement Trends That Will Influence Today's Culture") With E-Commerce and Social Media Marketing Relationship, Social networks, where consumers are increasingly shopping online, are connecting with various brands, and directing users to them. This gives us an important clue about the relationship between e-commerce and social media commerce. It is seen that ecommerce has started to become social media commerce with the effect of social media. Social media

marketing has been included in innovative marketing methods. will make it a huge e-commerce market.

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